

homothallism to heterothallism and then to the infertile state in which the sexual function might have been lost.

Southern Yunnan Province is a center of rice origin and has a long history of upland rice cultivation. The possibility that parasitic differentiation could be established from grasses to cultivated

rice (H. Kato's hypotheses) might have occurred in this area. The *Pyricularia* in this area exhibit the same properties as those of grass isolates (*E. indica*, *E. coracana*). Many isolates produced a lot of perithecia and produced sterile perithecia in single culture (see table). The formation rate of *Pyricularia*

becomes gradually less from south to north—from temperate to cool to cold regions—until it cannot form. The trend from high to low fertility corresponds with direction of the spread of rice cultivation. ■

Reaction of some rice germplasm to leaf blast (BI) in Guyana

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Blast caused by *Pyricularia grisea* is an important rice disease in Guyana. We screened 377 breeding lines for leaf BI resistance during Aug and Sep 1991. Breeding lines were grown in International Rice Blast Nurseries to score leaf BI reactions. Highly BI-susceptible variety Rustic was used as susceptible check and in spreader rows. Varieties Diwani and 6039 served as resistant checks.

Entries were inoculated at the four-leaf stage with chopped infected leaves. Nursery beds were irrigated twice a day between 1000 and 1100 h, and 1500 and 1600 h. Beds were covered with polyethylene sheets at night to maintain high humidity.

Reaction of rice breeding lines to blast (BI) in Guyana, 1991.

Breeding line	BI score ^a	BI reaction ^b	Origin	Breeding line	BI score ^a	BI reaction ^b	Origin
CT8008-3-5-2P-M	1	R	CIAT	IR54791-19-2-3	1	R	IRRI
CT8008-3-5-5P-M	1	R	CIAT	IR56382-123-3-1	3	MR	IRRI
CT8008-3-5-6P-M	1	R	CIAT	IR56383-46-1-2-1	3	MR	IRRI
CT8008-3-5-7P-M	1	R	CIAT	IR56446-94-3-1-2	1	R	IRRI
CT8008-3-5-8P-M	1	R	CIAT	NAR8 F ₂ -1-3-2	3	MR	Guyana
CT8222-4-1-8P-M	1	R	CIAT	NAR8 F ₂ -2-3-1	3	MR	Guyana
CT8238-6-14-P-M	1	R	CIAT	NAR9 F ₂ -1-3-2	5	MS	Guyana
CT8285-13-1-3P-M	1	R	CIAT	NAR12 F ₂ -1-2-3	5	MS	Guyana
CT8285-13-5-2P-M	1	R	CIAT	NAR126 F ₂ -2-1-1	3	MR	Guyana
Diwani	3	MR		NAR126 F ₄ -2-5-2	5	MS	Guyana
Surinam				NAR151 F ₄ -4-3	5	MS	Guyana
Eloni	3	MR		NAR210-1-1-4	1	R	Guyana
Surinam				NAR210-1-4	1	R	Guyana
IR8192-31-2-1-2	3	MR	IRRI	NAR218-2-4-4	3	MR	Guyana
IR44624-127-1-2-2-3	3	MR	IRRI	Pedigree 9	3	MR	Guyana
IR47761-27-1-36	1	R	IRRI	Pedigree 12	3	MR	Guyana
IR51678-93-2-2	5	MS	IRRI	TX06	5	MS	USA
IR52350-93-2-2	3	MR	IRRI	TX49 (Aromatic Lemont)	3	MR	USA
IR53306-36-1-3-1	1	R	IRRI	6039	3	MR	Guyana
IR53306-64-1-3-2	3	MR	IRRI				
IR53649-AC5-2	1	R	IRRI				

^aScored (0-9) using the Standard evaluation system for rice. ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, and MS = moderately susceptible.

Entries were scored on a scale of 0-9 using the Standard evaluation system for rice when the susceptible check had scored 7-9. Sixteen lines were resistant,

16 lines moderately resistant, and 6 lines moderately susceptible under conditions conducive to severe disease development (see table). ■

Resistance of BPH-resistant rice varieties to *S. furcifera* in the standard seedbox screening test (SSST) and modified seedbox screening test (MSST).^a

Variety	Genes for resistance to BPH	Plant damage rating ^b	
		SSST	MSST
IR47-B2-6	<i>Bph1</i>	9.0 a	9.0 a
Mudgo	<i>Bph1</i>	1.8 bc	1.0 a
Ptb18	<i>bph2</i>	9.0 a	1.0 b
Rathu Heenati	<i>Bph3</i>	1.0 c	1.0 b
Gambada Samba	<i>bph4</i>	1.0 c	1.0 b
Babawee	<i>bph4</i>	1.4 bc	1.0 b
ARC10550	<i>bph5</i>	1.8 bc	1.0 b
Swamalata	<i>bph6</i>	1.4 bc	1.0 b
Ptb21	<i>bph2 + Bph3</i>	1.0 c	1.0 b
Ptb33	<i>bph2 + Bph3</i>	1.4 bc	1.0 b
IR26	<i>Bph1</i>	9.0 a	9.0 a
IR36	<i>bph2</i>	9.0 a	1.0 b
IR56	<i>Bph3</i>	9.0 a	1.0 b
IR62	<i>Bph3</i>	2.2 b	1.0 b
IR64	<i>Bph1</i>	1.4 bc	1.0 b
TN1	No gene	9.0 a	9.0 a

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT; av of 5 replications.

^bDamage was rated on a 0-9 scale where 0-3 = resistant, 4-6 = moderately resistant, and 7-9 = susceptible.

Pest resistance— insects

Resistance to whitebacked planthopper (*Sogatella furcifera*) in rice varieties with different genes for brown planthopper (BPH) resistance

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We evaluated 15 BPH-resistant rice varieties for resistance to *S. furcifera* using the standard seedbox screening test (SSST) and modified seedbox screening test (MSST). The experiment was laid out